

Effect of Workability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance in The One-Stop Integrated of Investment and Labor Service Batu City

Devi Kristina¹, Harsono², M. C. Sina Setyadi³

¹Student Master of Management Program, University of Merdeka Malang, Indonesia

^{2,3}Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Merdeka Malang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the effect of Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance. This research is conclusive and classified as causal research using a quantitative approach. Data was collected through an online census using a questionnaire instrument. Respondents involved were as many as 60 people. The respondents were employees of the Investment Service One Stop Service and Manpower in Batu City, East Java Province. The data were processed using the multiple linear regression equation approaches with the SPSS program as the processor. Data analysis shows some relatively strong evidence to support the overall research hypothesis.

KEYWORDS: DPMTSP & NAKER, Batu City, Work Ability, Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In government in the public service sector, the quality of service is highly expected by the community. Quality of service according to the established Standard Operating Procedures. Services that are by the Standard Operating Procedures are a manifestation of the obligations of government officials, so services to the community provided by the bureaucracy should be characterized: as timely, accurate, and with procedures that are easy for the public to understand and follow. Various phenomena that occur in serving the community show how fragile trust is in the eyes of the public. This all happens because the apparatus has not 100% positioned itself as a government apparatus that fights for the needs and interests of the community.

The Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service and Human Resource Service for Batu City (DPMTSP & NAKER) are one of the agencies formed to deregulate and debureaucratize investment permits. DPMTSP & NAKER serves the community in the field of capital and various licenses such as building permits, trade permits, household business permits and others. Therefore, DPMTSP & NAKER employees are needed to maintain and improve performance in their work as a reference to determine performance at the Investment Service and One-Stop Integrated Services and Manpower in Batu City.

An interesting phenomenon in the One-Stop Integrated Services Investment Service and Manpower in Batu City, namely, first, public service providers in the field of licensing and non-licensing. In this case, the workability of employees is very influential on the quality of public services provided. Second, employee motivation can affect service quality so that the services provided can meet standard operating procedures. Third, the performance of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is in the public spotlight so that they can continue to provide excellent service to the community.

Based on the description above, the problem that needs to be examined is the effect of workability and work motivation on employee performance through job satisfaction at the One-Stop Integrated Services Investment Service and Manpower in Batu City.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Workability

Workability is the expertise possessed by an employee in carrying out his work or duties. Ability is a person's skills which include intelligence and skills in solving the problems they face (Wursanto, 2003:301). Thus workability is related to both physical and mental abilities or internal factors of an employee in carrying out his duties and work. According to Handoko (2001: 117), that ability is a determining factor for the success of personnel to maintain effective human resources. Thus that every employee can

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carry out his work assignments by the abilities that exist within and the type of work that is charged. According to Robbins (2006: 52), workability is an individual's capacity to carry out various tasks in a particular job. Where individual abilities are essentially composed of two factors, namely: intellectual abilities and physical abilities. According to Thoha (2011). Ability is one of the elements in maturity related to knowledge or skills that can be obtained from education, training and experience. Employability (Kaleta, 2010) refers to a complex feature and the extent reflects the interaction between the volume of both physical and mental activity and the functional abilities of workers, their health and the subjective assessment of their status in given organizational and social conditions.

2.2. Work Motivation

Sutrisno states (2012: 109), "Motivation is something that can encourage other people to want to carry out activities so that motivation is often seen as something that can encourage the behaviour of other people. Siagian (2002: 255) also says what other people want from their work, namely something that has a very important meaning for themselves and the institution/organization. Supardi (2004:47) states that motivation is a state in a person's personality that can encourage the will of each individual to carry out certain activities to achieve goals.

2.3. Job Satisfaction

According to Wexley & Yukl (in As'ad, 2002) what is called job satisfaction is a person's feelings towards his work. According to Howell & Dipboye (Munandar, 2001) views job satisfaction as the overall result of the degree of like or dislike of the workforce towards various aspects of their work. In other words, job satisfaction reflects the attitude of the workforce towards their work. Robbins & Coulter (Khalid, et al 2013) This refers to the general opinion of employees towards their work, such as; people with high levels of job satisfaction have positive feelings toward their jobs, whereas people who are unhappy with their jobs may hold negative attitudes. Job satisfaction has become the most significant and repeatedly studied attitude in the field of management science. According to Mitchel & Larsel Hoppock, (Athar, et al 2014) job satisfaction is a combined reaction based on psychological, physiological and environmental orders or disturbances that make an employee say whether he is satisfied or not. Based on several expert opinions, it can be concluded that job satisfaction is an attitude in the form of a reflection of the feelings of employees towards the whole job. Job satisfaction can be interpreted as the number of employees liking their work, employees who feel happy and satisfied with their work will of course carry out their duties as well as possible so that it will have a positive impact on their work results.

2.4. Performance

According to Mangkunegara (2004: 67), states "performance is job performance/actual performance or work performance that can be achieved by other people". Malayu S.P Hasibuan (2001:94) characterizes the implementation of work or execution as a job that is completed by members of the organization in response to the mandate given to them depending on ability, experience and timeliness. Performance is a result of a series of activities that are indicated for a certain time according to binding policies (Edison 2016: 190). Furthermore, performance based on the opinion version of Robbins (2015: 187) is interpreted as a function of exchange between abilities and incentives. Rifai (2015: 406) states: "performance means the execution of a job. Another opinion, Rivai and Basri (2005:15), performance is an achievement as well as the level of achievement of other people as a whole in an uncertain period in completing obligations compared to results that may be different, for example, work principles, targets or actions that have just been completed.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Respondent Population and Sampling Technique

The population of respondents in the ongoing research this time are employees of the One-Stop Service Investment and Manpower Service in Batu City, East Java Province. The total number of 60 respondents. Considering the relatively small number of members of the population, all members of the population become the object of research. The method used is a census of all respondents.

3.2. Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis test in the ongoing research this time uses the following techniques:

1. Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables

This study used the frequency distribution to describe each indicator item and variable. This analysis leads to defining the variables as a whole.

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2. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis is used to observe the impact of Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job satisfaction on their correlation with Employee Performance. Regression analysis was processed using the SPSS program with the equation:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \epsilon$$

Information:

- Y = Employee Performance
- α = Constant
- $\beta_1... \beta_3$ = Regression Coefficient
- X_1 = Work Ability
- X_2 = Work Motivation
- X_3 = Job Satisfaction
- ϵ = Error

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Multiple Linear Regression

The results of primary data processing using the SPSS 26 program are presented below :

Table 1. Recapitulation of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variables	Regression Coefficient	t Statistik	Significance	Result
Work Ability	0.1763	2.8790	0.0060	Significant
Work Motivation	0.1211	2.6730	0.0100	Significant
Job Satisfaction	0.0640	2.0000	0.0450	Significant
Constant	-1.9985	-1.2150	0.2290	
R	0.7930			
R Square	0.6290			
Adjusted R Square	0.6100			
F Statistik	31.6980			
Sig.	0.0010			
Dependent Variable	Y Employee Performance			
F Table	2.7700			
t Table	2.0032			

Based on these provisions, the equation of the multiple linear regression model in this research is:

$$Y = -1,9985 + ,1763X_1 + ,1211X_2 + ,0640X_3 + e$$

The regression coefficient for the Work Ability variable is .1763 and is positive, meaning that increasing Work Ability will further improve Employee Performance. The results of partial hypothesis testing for the effect of variable X1 on Y yield a significant value of 0.0056 which is smaller than 0.05. The second conclusion is that Ha is accepted. This shows that workability has a significant influence on employee performance. This is in line with research on the relationship between the variable workability (X1) and employee performance (Y) which was stated by Ferra (2020) with the research results. All variables and questionnaire items are valid that Talent management, Knowledge management and Employee retention affect employee performance at Kanjuruhan University Malang.

The regression coefficient for the Work Motivation variable is .1211 and is positive, meaning that the better the work motivation is, the better the employee performance will be. The results of testing the hypothesis partially for the effect of variable X2 on Y produce a significant value of 0.0098 which is smaller than 0.05. The second conclusion is that Ha is accepted. This shows that Employee Motivation has a significant influence on Employee Performance. This is in line with research on the link between the variable work motivation (X2) and employee performance (Y) which was stated by Abdul Aziz Nugraha Pratama and Aprina Wardani (2017) with the results of research on workability partially having no effect and not significant on employee performance. while work morale and job satisfaction partially have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

The regression coefficient for the Job Satisfaction variable is .0640 and is positive, meaning that the higher the level of Job Satisfaction, the higher the Employee Performance. The results of testing the hypothesis partially for the effect of variable X3 on Y produce a significant value of 0.0453 which is smaller than 0.05. The conclusion of both is that Ha is accepted. This shows that Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance. This is in line with research on the link between the variables Job satisfaction (X3) on Employee Performance (Y) which has been stated by Ayu Desi Indrawati the effect

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of job satisfaction and customer satisfaction on employee performance in private hospitals in Denpasar City (2013) with the results of Job Satisfaction research has a significant positive influence on employee performance.

The results of partial hypothesis testing for the effect of the independent variables X1, X2, and X3 on the dependent variable Y are also used to find dominance among these independent variables on the dependent variable. The results are shown by the variable X1 Work Ability to be the most dominant influence on employee performance. This is shown by the Standardized coefficients with a value of .3899 or a percentage of 38.99%.

The results of simultaneous hypothesis testing for the effect of the independent variables X1, X2, and X3 on the dependent variable Y yield a significant value of .00 <.05. The conclusion is that H_a is accepted. This shows that Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction together have a positive and significant influence on Employee Performance.

The R-value in the regression model was obtained at 0.7930 indicating a very strong relationship between the variables Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance variables.

The same result also shows that the value of R^2 in the regression model is 0.6294, which means that the variables of Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction give a percentage contribution of 62.94% to Employee Performance. While the remaining 37.06% was contributed by other variables outside the research model.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

The results of the research based on the Regression Coefficient and Significance Values in the multiple linear analysis test conclude that Work Ability has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. The ability of employees within the Batu City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services and Manpower Service (DPMPTSP & NAKER) is based on the selection of admissions. Acceptance selection is the key to the initial standard of each employee's workability. The guideline is none other than educational background, age, interests, experience, and other selections that make up the series of recipients. The placement of employees is also important considering that the suitability between the placement and the background in question is very closely related to their work abilities. The workability of an employee also has a close relationship with performance. If an employee has good abilities, at least there is the hope of good performance as well. Increasing workability will further improve employee performance.

The results of the research based on the Regression Coefficient and Significance Values in the multiple linear analysis test concluded that Work Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Work Motivation within the Batu City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service and Manpower Service (DPMPTSP & NAKER) environment play an important role in shaping good performance. The high work motivation of employees at least fosters hope for good performance. An employee is always positively motivated, so new ideas should always be sparked, innovations will always be carried out, as well as creativity that is always surging and always there. The guarantee is excellent performance. Promising employee performance, it is not impossible that work targets will be achieved and even exceeded. Motivation can come from many directions, internally because of interest, compatibility in placement, linearity with a scientific background, commensurate salary, bonuses, incentives, etc. Or from external sources, for example, support from the work environment, good leaders, a positive circle of friends, etc. The better the provision of Work Motivation, the more it will improve Employee Performance.

The results of the study based on the Regression Coefficient and Significance Values in multiple linear analysis tests conclude that Job Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance. Job Satisfaction in the Batu City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services and Manpower Service (DPMPTSP & NAKER) environment can be felt when an employee feels confident in his abilities, full of positive enthusiasm, able to complete targets, workload, challenges, and obstacles in the process, it was at that point that he felt he became a full-fledged employee. Job satisfaction is formed naturally, personally, and non-material. A higher level of Job Satisfaction will further improve Employee Performance.

The results of partial hypothesis testing for the influence of the independent variables Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction, on the dependent variable Performance, are also used to find dominance among these independent variables on the dependent variable. The results are shown by the variable Work Ability to be the most dominant influence on employee performance.

The results of testing the hypothesis simultaneously for the effect of the independent variables X1, X2, and X3 on the dependent variable Y show that Work Ability, Work Motivation, and Job Satisfaction together have a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance.

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5.2. Suggestion

To improve superior performance quality between employees' ability to complete work that has become their responsibility, employee motivation in completing tasks, and employee satisfaction, it is necessary to hold a reward program for exemplary employees to increase employee motivation in the next period. Training and socialization also need to be held to improve the soft skills and hard skills of the employees concerned.

Based on the research results, it can be seen that the effect of workability, work motivation, and job satisfaction on performance in DPMTSP & NAKER can be additional knowledge in various sectors.

If further researchers are interested in similar topics, they should further expand other variables and increase the number of samples. Apart from that, to strengthen the research data, it can also be added by conducting interviews with research samples so that the information obtained is not limited to questionnaires in the form of closed questions.

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